

INNOVATIVE BEHAVIOR MODEL USING INTERVENING KNOWLEDGE SHARING: EVIDENCE FROM JAKARTA ISLAMIC HOSPITAL

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Abstract

This study aims to identify and analyze the role of knowledge sharing in mediating the influence of Islamic leadership and digital literacy on the innovative behavior of healthcare workers at Jakarta Islamic Hospital. A quantitative approach was employed to ensure objective and measurable results. The study targeted a population of 1,396 healthcare workers, from which a representative sample of 230 respondents was selected using a proportionate random sampling technique. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire based on a five-point Likert scale to capture the perceptions and attitudes of participants. For data analysis, the study utilized Structural Equation Modeling with the Partial Least Squares method (SEM-PLS), which is appropriate for examining complex relationships among latent variables. The results demonstrate that both Islamic leadership and digital literacy exert a direct and significant positive influence on the innovative behavior of healthcare workers. Moreover, knowledge sharing is also found to have a strong and positive effect on innovative behavior. The study further reveals that Islamic leadership and digital literacy positively and significantly influence knowledge sharing practices within the hospital setting. This indicates that leaders who embody Islamic values and employees with strong digital competencies are more likely to engage in sharing knowledge. Additionally, knowledge sharing is confirmed to be a significant mediating variable that strengthens the impact of Islamic leadership and digital literacy on innovative behavior. These findings highlight the importance of fostering a culture of trust, continuous learning, and technological readiness to enhance innovation in healthcare institutions.

Keywords: Islamic Leadership, Digital Literacy, Knowledge Sharing, Innovative Behavior.

INTRODUCTION

Hospitals play a strategic role in realizing a healthy and advanced society due to their responsibility in providing vital, complex, and specialized healthcare services (Mohebi et al., 2022). The quality of healthcare services is a major concern for healthcare providers worldwide (Darzi et al., 2023), prompting the continuous development of the healthcare industry in line with the growing awareness of the importance of quality services (Mensah et al., 2023).

In today's environment, characterized by rapid change and disruption, it is crucial to have employees who are innovative in their work. This is especially true for public service institutions, where innovation is necessary to address complex and ever-changing challenges, requiring organizations to be agile and adaptive (Lnnee & Kim, 2024). In this context, individual innovative behavior is key to enhancing efficiency and supporting long-term organizational sustainability. The innovative behavior of organizational members serves as an

essential source of organizational innovation and a driver of sustainable competitiveness, ultimately leading to an innovative organization (Montani, Courcy, & Vandenberghe, 2017; Ren & Zhang, 2015; Newman, Tse, Schwarz, & Nielsen, 2018; Wang & Dass, 2017)

To optimize innovative behavior, a comprehensive understanding of the various influencing factors is essential. Based on previous studies, several key factors that play an important role in promoting innovative behavior include leadership (Rosing et al., 2011; Günzel-Jensen et al., 2018; Hansen dan Pihl-Thingvad, 2018; Febriani dan Sa'diyah, 2021), knowledge sharing (Nguyen et al., 2020; Kmiecik, 2020), and digital literacy (Pilav-Velić et al., 2021; Putra et al., 2023). Effective leadership is crucial in encouraging organizational members to work harder and become more innovative. Leaders must be able to provide motivation and inspiration to stimulate their subordinates' creative ideas. According to Pieterse et al. (2010), leadership serves as a source of inspiration and motivation for organizational members—both of which are essential in fostering innovative behavior.

Knowledge also plays a crucial role in encouraging innovative behavior; therefore, organizations need to promote a culture and attitude of knowledge sharing among employees. Innovation is one of the core capabilities required by organizations to achieve and maintain competitive advantage, which is greatly influenced by the extent of knowledge exchange among employees (Castaneda & Cuellar, 2020). Knowledge sharing is an interaction between human actors in which the raw material is knowledge itself. It also refers to the ability to transfer experiences, information, and expert insights into practice (Wiewiora et al., 2013).

Digital literacy is another important resource that drives innovative behavior. This aligns with the rapid development of communication, information, and digital technologies, which demand that individuals possess adequate digital literacy to stay informed and leverage technology as a source of knowledge. Organizational members must have sufficient digital literacy to positively utilize digital advancements to explore knowledge that can support task completion. A study by Pilav-Velić et al. (2021) indicates that digital literacy promotes digital practices, which in turn positively impact innovative behavior.

Based on a review of previous studies, several research gaps have been identified, making this study significant. First, no previous research has simultaneously investigated Islamic leadership, knowledge sharing, digital literacy, and innovative behavior within a single model. Previous studies have only examined these variables partially. Second, no prior research has examined these variables within the context of hospitals, meaning there is a lack of information regarding the causal relationships among them. Third, previous research has shown inconsistent findings regarding the effects of these variables. For instance, studies by Nguyen et al. (2020) and Kmiecik (2020) found that knowledge sharing influences innovative behavior, whereas Zhao et al. (2020) reported that knowledge sharing activities such as inbound knowledge sharing had no effect on innovation. This study seeks to address these gaps, and the investigation into the mediating role of knowledge sharing in the relationship between Islamic leadership and digital literacy on the innovative behavior of healthcare professionals represents a relatively new and important research area, especially in the context of major transformations in the healthcare sector.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Islamic Leadership and Knowledge Sharing

Islamic leadership emphasizes values such as honesty, justice, and responsibility, which foster a safe work environment for knowledge sharing. An Islamic leader acts as a role model in disseminating knowledge, as encouraged in Islamic teachings that promote advising one another and spreading goodness.

Through a spiritual and moral approach, an Islamic leader builds trust, which serves as a crucial foundation for the process of knowledge sharing among members of the organization. The values of *ukhuwah* (brotherhood) and *amanah* (trustworthiness) in Islamic leadership also strengthen individual motivation to support one another through the exchange of knowledge for mutual progress.

In Islamic values, one of the core principles is the virtue of sharing or giving (*sadaqah*) to others. Several commands and virtues of giving in the Qur'an are found in Surah Al-Baqarah verse 267, Surah Al-Baqarah verse 261, Surah Al-Munafiqun verse 10, and Surah Ali Imran verse 134. In Islam, *sadaqah* is not limited to material wealth but also includes non-material contributions such as beneficial knowledge shared with others.

Sharing good knowledge with others is considered an act of *amal jariyah*—a continuous charity that brings ongoing rewards even after the giver has passed away. This highlights that knowledge sharing holds high spiritual value and is a noble form of contribution toward building a knowledgeable and moral society.

Previous research has shown that leadership is a factor influencing knowledge sharing. For instance, Park dan Kim (2018) found that transformational leadership directly influences the climate and behavior of knowledge sharing. Studies Kim and Park (2020) and Saeed et al. (2022) also reported that certain leadership styles, such as transformational leadership, have a direct effect on knowledge sharing behavior. Based on the above explanation, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H1: Islamic leadership has a direct effect on knowledge sharing.

Digital Literacy and Knowledge Sharing

Amid the rapid development of technology today, digital literacy has become an essential skill for every individual in the workplace. Digital literacy provides the foundational skills necessary for individuals to access, manage, and disseminate information effectively in digital environments.

This capability strengthens a culture of knowledge sharing by facilitating the exchange of information through various technological platforms, such as online forums, social media, or knowledge management systems. With strong digital literacy, individuals become more confident and critical in sharing accurate and useful information. This fosters a collaborative work environment where knowledge is not held individually but shared for the collective benefit.

The relationship between digital literacy and knowledge sharing can be understood through the theory of metaliteracy, which emphasizes that digital literacy includes the understanding, production, and active sharing of knowledge within online communities (Mackey & Jacobson, 2011). Previous studies also show that information and digital literacy skills have a positive and significant effect on enhancing knowledge sharing (Sulehri et al., 2024). Other research indicates that digital literacy is a positive and significant predictor of knowledge sharing and academic performance (Salimi et al., 2025). Therefore, digital literacy is a crucial factor in promoting knowledge sharing. Based on this explanation, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H2: Digital literacy has a direct effect on knowledge sharing.

Innovative behavior

Innovation is a crucial factor that determines the survival of an organization. According to Hill and Hult (2018, p. 68), “innovation is the development of new products, processes, organizations, management practices, and strategies.” Thus, innovation is not limited to the creation of new products but can also be seen in work processes and the strategies implemented. The innovation process within an organization depends on the human resources it possesses. In other words, innovative behavior becomes the key to building an innovative organization.

Innovative behavior relates to how actively individuals create, support, and apply new ideas, including developing plans and exploring new technologies, processes, or products (Neiva et al., 2017), and is associated with the deliberate effort by employees to introduce or apply new ideas, products, processes, or procedures in their job, team, or organization (Yuan & Woodman, 2010). Innovative behavior also means turning creativity into advantage and is evident when employees use different new ways and ideas in their work (Mokhber, et al., 2015).

According to Sørensen and Torfing (2011), innovative behavior involves a four-stage process. First, idea generation includes identifying problems, clarifying goals, and challenging assumptions to develop and share new ideas. Second, idea selection focuses on choosing impactful yet feasible ideas through negotiation and compromise. Third, implementation turns ideas into actionable changes, requiring leadership and adaptability. Fourth, dissemination ensures the spread of innovations by demonstrating their benefits and addressing resistance across or between organizations.

Meanwhile, Kleysen and Street (2001) identified five dimensions of innovative behavior: opportunity exploration, generativity, informative investigation, championing, and application. Opportunity exploration involves broadly understanding and recognizing new possibilities, including gathering information about innovation opportunities. Generativity focuses on creating ideas, solutions, and information combinations that promote organizational growth. Informative investigation includes formulating, demonstrating, and evaluating ideas to shape concrete solutions. Championing involves social behaviors such as persuading, influencing, negotiating, and taking risks to realize innovation. The application stage emphasizes implementing, modifying, and embedding the developed ideas or innovations.

Islamic Leadership and Innovative Behavior

In Islam, leadership is considered one of the most important elements in shaping and guiding a community, organization, and state (Zaim et al., 2022). According to Galanou and Farrag (2015), the Islamic approach integrates business life with religious life and proposes a virtue-centered view of leadership, characterized by moral values, spirituality, ethics, and wisdom. From an Islamic perspective, leadership can be defined as the act of guiding, directing, leading, and showing the path that is approved by Allah S.W.T. What distinguishes Islamic leadership from others is its emphasis on values taught in Islam and its orientation toward seeking the pleasure of Allah. Islamic leadership is neither absolute nor authoritarian, as Islam promotes a balanced approach (Ikhwan, 2018).

According to Ahmad and Ogunsola (2011), the principles of Islamic leadership are primarily derived from the Qur'an, the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him), and his companions, to guide governance and the construction of ethical and effective leadership. In Islam, the role model for leadership is the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH). There are four main characteristics of his leadership that must be emulated: *Siddiq*, *Amanah*, *Tabligh*, and *Fathanah*. *Siddiq* refers to the Prophet's truthfulness in accepting the truth from Allah, which means that all of his actions, words, behaviors, emotions, and even silence were truthful. In leadership, this translates to honesty and integrity in making decisions and taking responsibility. *Amanah* means being trustworthy. The Prophet always delivered any message as it was revealed, without altering or omitting anything. *Tabligh*, or delivering the message, reflects the duty of conveying and explaining Allah's revelation. *Fathanah* refers to wisdom and intelligence, in contrast to ignorance or foolishness.

These characteristics of Islamic leadership can be applied to encourage innovative behavior. Islam encourages its followers to continuously improve themselves over time. Essentially, Islam is a teaching that not only emphasizes ritual worship but also encourages its followers to seek happiness both in this world and in the hereafter. Allah S.W.T clearly states that human beings hold the key to their own improvement, as indicated in Surah Ar-Ra'd (13), verse 11: *"Indeed, Allah will not change the condition of a people until they change what is in themselves."* This verse emphasizes that humans must think and use their intellect to continually improve their circumstances. The Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) also encouraged self-improvement, as stated in the hadith: *"Whoever's today is better than yesterday is among the fortunate; whoever's today is the same as yesterday is among the losers; and whoever's today is worse than yesterday is among the wretched."* (HR Al-Hakim)

Previous studies have provided evidence that Islamic leadership is associated with innovative behavior. For example, research by Febriani and Sa'diyah (2021) indicates that Islamic leadership positively and significantly contributes to innovative behavior. Thus, it is evident that a leader can apply and instill Islamic values to shape the attitudes and behaviors of subordinates, one of which is aimed at fostering innovative behavior. Therefore, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H3: Islamic leadership has a direct effect on innovative behavior.

Digital Literacy and Innovative Behavior

Gilster (1997) explained that digital literacy is the ability to use technology and information through digital means efficiently and effectively in various contexts such as careers and academics. Martin and Grudziecki (2006) described digital literacy as being related to an individual's awareness, attitudes, and abilities in appropriately using digital tools to access, manage, evaluate, and create information, communicate, and build knowledge within specific life contexts for constructive social action. According to Bawden (2001), digital literacy includes the ability to assemble knowledge from reliable sources, think critically about information, understand non-linear materials, be aware of the role of conventional and digital media, make use of network access, filter the truth of information, and feel comfortable communicating and publishing information digitally.

Suwarto et al. (2022) in their study measured digital literacy using three aspects: technical skills, cognitive skills, and socio-emotional skills. Technical skills can be described as the ability to perform tasks through digital platforms with technical and operational proficiency. Vodā et al. (2022) explained that cognitive skills include the selection of platforms to manage digital information and concern for legal and ethical contexts. Meanwhile, Calvani et al. (2009) stated that multidimensional attributes are part of cognitive skills in digital literacy, namely the ability to read, select, interpret, and evaluate data and information while considering its reliability.

The socio-emotional aspect relates to interacting with others, collaborating, and performing daily tasks using online platforms, which is covered under socio-emotional skills (Ng, 2012). This can be achieved by adhering to ethical standards when using digital platforms to prevent misunderstandings, protect personal information confidentiality, and respond appropriately when dealing with any issues that may arise on digital platforms (Eliezer & Enuma, 2019)s. Digital literacy is essential for promoting innovative behavior because it enables individuals to navigate, evaluate, and create information effectively using digital technology.

Digital literacy plays a key role in information access, allowing individuals to access diverse information online, which can inspire new ideas and perspectives that lead to innovation. It also encourages critical thinking, helping individuals develop analytical and evaluative skills necessary for innovative problem-solving. Previous research by Pilav-Velić et al. (2021) proved that digital literacy positively contributes to enhancing innovative behavior. Therefore, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H4: Digital literacy has a direct influence on innovative behavior.

Knowledge Sharing and Innovative Behavior

According to Thalmann et al. (2024), knowledge is a key resource for companies that must be managed and protected from risks. Casimir et al. (2012) explain that knowledge sharing refers to a positive activity that contributes to the competitiveness of an organization. Knowledge sharing is also related to an individual's willingness within the organization to share their knowledge with others (Bock et al., 2005).

Therefore, knowledge is an important asset that must be protected and voluntarily shared by individuals within the organization to enhance the company's competitiveness. Knowledge sharing can be part of a competency framework and is manifested through several indicators, such as being enthusiastic about sharing knowledge with colleagues, taking proactive steps to organize group meetings for exchanging relevant information and knowledge, building networks that enable knowledge sharing activities, and ensuring that the knowledge received is codified, recorded, and disseminated through the internet or other communication tools (Armstrong, 2006).

Strong knowledge-sharing behavior within an organization facilitates the enhancement of individual knowledge and skills that are beneficial in work processes, including fostering the emergence of individual innovative behavior. Innovation requires prerequisites such as sufficient knowledge, skills, and information. Knowledge-sharing activities can fulfill these needs, making it a vital asset for encouraging innovative behavior.

The important role of knowledge sharing in enhancing innovative behavior can be seen from Tan's explanation as cited. The knowledge-sharing process plays a central role in knowledge management, as it helps ensure that available knowledge resources are optimally utilized to support improved organizational performance (Yeboah, 2023). ackson et al. (2003) stated that knowledge sharing promotes broad learning and prevents resource waste caused by repeatedly solving the same problems, while knowledge hoarding is considered a dysfunctional behavior.

Knowledge sharing is also deemed crucial in generating business opportunities from the creation of new ideas that enhance performance (Xue et al., 2011). Previous studies by Radaelli et al. (2014), Asurakkody and Kim (2020) also found that knowledge sharing has a positive effect on innovative behavior. Therefore, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H5: Knowledge sharing has a direct effect on innovative behavior.

Based on the theoretical description and results of previous studies explained above, the theoretical framework can be described as follows.

Figure 1: Theoretical framework

RESEARCH METHODS

The study was conducted at Jakarta Islamic Hospital with healthcare workers as the research subjects. A quantitative approach was used to examine the influence of Islamic leadership and digital literacy on innovative behavior, with knowledge sharing as the mediating variable. Data collection was carried out using a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire, consisting of: strongly disagree (1), disagree (2), neutral (3), agree (4), and strongly agree (5). The researcher used the SPSS Sample Power application to determine the required sample size, applying statistical assumptions such as a 5% maximum error probability and 80% test power (Nematollahi et al., 2024). Based on the calculation a total sample of 230 was obtained taken using proportionate random sampling technique.

This study employed two stages of data analysis: the measurement model and the structural model. In the first stage, the measurement model was evaluated through tests of convergent validity, discriminant validity, and reliability. Convergent validity was assessed using cross-loading factors and the Average Variance Extracted (AVE), with a minimum threshold of 0.7 for loadings and 0.5 for AVE—although loadings between 0.5 and 0.6 may still be accepted for models in the development phase. Discriminant validity was tested by comparing construct loadings and the square root of the AVE, which must be greater than the correlation between the construct and other constructs. Furthermore, internal consistency reliability was measured using Composite Reliability and Cronbach’s Alpha, where values above 0.7 indicated good reliability. The second stage involved structural model analysis using the PLS-SEM method via SmartPLS, and the significance of structural paths was tested using bootstrapping. The significance criteria were based on p-values compared with $\alpha = 0.05$ and 0.01.

RESULTS

Demographic information

Demographic information provides an overview of the distribution of health worker samples consisting of gender, age, education and length of service.

Table 1: Demographic Information

Demographic Attributes	Frequency	Percent	Demographic Attributes	Frequency	Percent
Gender			Education		
Male	195	84.8	Diploma	96	41.7
Female	35	15.2	Bachelor Degree	129	56.1
			Graduate School	5	2.2
Age			Tenure		
≤ 30 years	96	41.7	≤2 years	53	23
31-40 years	64	27.8	3-5 years	36	15.7
41-50 years	47	20.4	6-10 years	28	12.2
>50 years	23	10	11-20 years	59	25.7
			> 20 years	54	23.5

Source: Data processed

The demographic data shows that the majority of respondents were male, comprising 84.8%, while females made up only 15.2% of the sample. In terms of age, most participants were 30 years old or younger (41.7%), followed by those aged 31–40 years (27.8%).

Regarding educational background, over half of the respondents held a bachelor’s degree (56.1%), while 41.7% had a diploma, and only a small portion (2.2%) had attended graduate school. For tenure, the largest group had worked for 11–20 years (25.7%), followed by those with over 20 years of experience (23.5%). This demographic profile indicates a relatively young and experienced workforce, with a strong educational foundation.

Descriptive statistics

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation=SD) and correlation results for each constructs.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics

	Mean	SD	IL	DL	KS	IB
Islamic leadership (IL)	3.868	0.553				
Digital literacy (DL)	3.924	0.544	0.674**			
Knowledge sharing (KS)	3.940	0.551	0.647**	0.755**		
Innovative behavior (IB)	3.811	0.438	0.677**	0.736**	0.715**	
<i>** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level</i>						

Source: Data processed

The mean scores of all variables range between 3.811 and 3.940, indicating generally high perceptions among respondents on a 5-point scale. Digital literacy and knowledge sharing have the highest mean values, suggesting that respondents feel confident in their digital abilities and willingness to share knowledge.

The correlation coefficients show strong and significant positive relationships ($p < 0.01$) among all variables. Notably, digital literacy is positively and highest correlated with innovative behavior ($r = 0.736$), indicating that higher digital literacy are associated with increased innovative behavior among individuals.

Measurements model

Before testing the hypothesis to predict the influence between latent variables in the structural model, it is important to first evaluate the measurement model to verify the validity and reliability of the indicators and latent variables to be tested further. Evaluation of the measurement model includes convergent validity, discriminant validity, and reliability testing.

Convergent validity indicates how well different measurement items intended to assess the same concept produce similar results. It is assessed through outer loading values, where a value greater than 0.7 indicates that the indicator is valid.

At the construct level, convergent validity is evaluated using Average Variance Extracted (AVE), which measures the amount of variance captured by a construct relative to the variance due to measurement error.

Table 3: Convergent validity

Variable	Indicator	Loading Factor	AVE
Islamic Leadership (IL)	IL1	0.831	0,632
	IL2	0.751	
	IL3	0.787	
	IL4	0.810	
	IL5	0.804	
	IL6	0.738	
	IL7	0.807	
	IL8	0.836	
	IL9	0.827	
	IL10	0.754	
Digital Literacy (DL)	DL1	0.830	0,646
	DL2	0.803	
	DL3	0.792	
	DL4	0.782	
	DL5	0.798	
	DL6	0.770	
	DL7	0.813	
	DL8	0.837	
Knowledge Sharing (KS)	KS1	0.822	0,652
	KS2	0.769	
	KS3	0.809	
	KS4	0.761	
	KS5	0.818	
	KS6	0.806	
	KS7	0.851	
	KS8	0.819	
Innovative Behavior (IB)	IB1	0.809	0,621
	IB2	0.809	
	IB3	0.780	
	IB4	0.814	
	IB5	0.750	
	IB6	0.784	
	IB7	0.774	
	IB8	0.800	
	IB9	0.805	
	IB10	0.750	

Source: Data processed

The results of the convergent validity test show that all indicators for each variable have loading factors above 0.7, indicating that the indicators are valid in measuring their respective constructs. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values for all constructs—Islamic Leadership (0.632), Digital Literacy (0.646), Knowledge Sharing (0.652), and Innovative Behavior (0.621)—exceed the minimum threshold of 0.5. This suggests that each construct captures a sufficient proportion of variance from its indicators compared to measurement error. Therefore, all constructs in this study meet the criteria for convergent validity and are considered to have good measurement quality.

The results of the discriminant validity test indicate that each measurement indicator loads more highly on its corresponding latent variable than on any other construct, as shown in Table 4. Additionally, the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) (Table 5) for each construct exceeds the correlations it has with other constructs in the model. These findings confirm that each construct is empirically distinct and measures what it is intended to measure without overlapping with other variables. Therefore, all measurement scales used in this study satisfy the established criteria for discriminant validity, ensuring the model's robustness and clarity in construct differentiation.

Table 4: Discriminant validity

Indicators	Islamic Leadership	Digital Literacy	Knowledge Sharing	Innovative Behavior
IL1	0.831	0.524	0.556	0.574
IL2	0.751	0.528	0.506	0.533
IL3	0.787	0.500	0.523	0.497
IL4	0.810	0.558	0.584	0.553
IL5	0.804	0.505	0.539	0.575
IL6	0.738	0.448	0.450	0.487
IL7	0.807	0.522	0.536	0.584
IL8	0.836	0.582	0.627	0.565
IL9	0.827	0.516	0.544	0.518
IL10	0.754	0.469	0.500	0.492
DL1	0.531	0.830	0.583	0.592
DL2	0.480	0.803	0.621	0.565
DL3	0.565	0.792	0.609	0.540
DL4	0.542	0.782	0.566	0.552
DL5	0.482	0.798	0.578	0.541
DL6	0.486	0.770	0.591	0.581
DL7	0.548	0.813	0.685	0.632
DL8	0.538	0.837	0.658	0.616
KS1	0.572	0.618	0.822	0.579
KS2	0.457	0.634	0.769	0.614
KS3	0.531	0.588	0.809	0.558
KS4	0.525	0.545	0.761	0.634
KS5	0.597	0.613	0.818	0.587
KS6	0.494	0.612	0.806	0.597
KS7	0.646	0.694	0.851	0.626
KS8	0.540	0.616	0.819	0.581
IB1	0.531	0.601	0.589	0.809
IB2	0.555	0.573	0.604	0.809
IB3	0.533	0.564	0.568	0.780
IB4	0.527	0.582	0.610	0.814
IB5	0.435	0.512	0.519	0.750
IB6	0.581	0.567	0.598	0.784
IB7	0.491	0.516	0.569	0.774
IB8	0.625	0.591	0.651	0.800
IB9	0.519	0.604	0.553	0.805
IB10	0.522	0.556	0.554	0.750

Source: Data processed

Table 5: Correlation coefficients and the square root of the AVE

Constructs	IL	DL	KS	IB
Islamic leadership	0.795			
Digital literacy	0.650	0.803		
Knowledge sharing	0.677	0.763	0.807	
Innovative behavior	0.678	0.720	0.740	0.788
Note: The number in bold and diagonal are the square root of the AVE				

Source: Data processed

Reliability results show that all constructs in this study have Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values above 0.9, indicating excellent reliability. Cronbach's Alpha values ranged from 0.921 to 0.935, indicating that the items in each construct are internally consistent.

Similarly, Composite Reliability values ranging from 0.936 to 0.945 indicate that the constructs can be relied upon to measure the intended variables. These high reliability values strengthen the validity of the measurement results in this study.

Thus, the four constructs—Islamic leadership, digital literacy, knowledge sharing, and innovative behavior—are declared to have excellent measurement quality.

Table 6: Construct reliability

Constructs	Cronbach's α	Composite Reliability
Islamic leadership	0.935	0.945
Digital literacy	0.921	0.936
Knowledge sharing	0.923	0.937
Innovative behavior	0.932	0.942

Source: Data processed

Structural model

In order to test the hypothesis, we use SEM PLS which is processed with SmartPLS 4 to examine the structural paths and the R-square for each endogenous variables and the results as seen in Figure 2 and Table 7 and Table 8.

Table 7: Path coefficients of direct effects

Variables	Innovative behavior			Knowledge sharing		
	B	t	p-value	β	t	p-value
Islamic leadership	0.255*	2.535	0.011	0.314**	3.444	0.001
Digital literacy	0.291**	2.565	0.010	0.559**	6.306	0.000
Knowledge sharing	0.345**	2.755	0.006			
R ²	0.638			0.640		
* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$						

Source: Data processed

Figure 2: Results of path coefficients

Table 8: Path coefficients of indirect effects

Indirect effects	B	t	p-value
Islamic leadership > Knowledge sharing > innovative Behavior	0.108**	2.368	0.018
Digital literacy > Knowledge sharing > innovative Behavior	0.193**	2.257	0.024

*p < 0.05, **p < 0.01

Source: Data processed

The path coefficient (β) between Islamic leadership and innovative behavior is 0.255 with p-value $0.011 < 0.05$, so that supported hypothesis 1. It means Islamic leadership had a significance positive effect on healthcare workers innovative behavior. Digital literacy and

innovative behavior indicate path coefficient 0.291 with *p-value* $0.010 < 0.05$, which means supported hypothesis 2, so that digital literacy had a significance positive effect on healthcare workers innovative behavior. The effect of knowledge sharing on innovative behavior indicated by path coefficient 0.345 with *p-value* $0.006 < 0.05$, which means supported hypothesis 3. This means knowledge sharing had a significance positive effect on healthcare workers innovative behavior. Further, for the effect of Islamic leadership on knowledge sharing had path coefficient 0.314 with *p-value* $0.001 < 0.05$, which means rejected supported 4. This means that Islamic leadership had impact on healthcare workers knowledge sharing. While for the effect of digital literacy on knowledge sharing indicated by path coefficient 0.559 with *p-value* $0.000 < 0.05$, therefore supported hypothesis 5. This means that digital literacy had a significance positive impact on healthcare workers knowledge sharing. R-square for the endogenous variable of innovative behavior is 0.638 that explained 63.8% variance of innovative behavior determinate by Islamic leadership, digital literacy, and knowledge sharing. While R-square for the endogenous variable of knowledge sharing is 0.640 that explained 64% variance of knowledge sharing determinate by Islamic leadership and digital literacy.

Furthermore, the mediating effect of Islamic leadership on innovative behavior through knowledge sharing yields a path coefficient of 0.108 with a *p-value* of $0.018 < 0.05$, indicating a significant mediation effect. Thus, knowledge sharing significantly mediates the influence of Islamic leadership on innovative behavior. While for the mediating effect of digital literacy on innovative behavior through knowledge sharing indicated by a path coefficient of 0.193 with *p-value* of $0.024 < 0.05$, indicating its significant mediation effect. Thus, knowledge sharing significantly mediates the influence of digital literacy on innovative behavior.

DISCUSSION

This study demonstrates that Islamic leadership significantly contributes to innovative behavior. Islamic leaders play a crucial role in instilling vision, inspiring, and encouraging innovation in the workplace. An appropriate leadership style creates an atmosphere conducive to exploration and sharing of ideas. Islamic leadership aligns with Islamic teachings, which encourage people to continuously develop and improve themselves. Surah Ar-Ra'd, verse 11, and the Prophet's hadith emphasize the importance of continuous change and self-improvement. Therefore, Islamic values can shape innovative attitudes and behaviors within organizations. Previous studies have also provided evidence that Islamic leadership is linked to innovative behavior. For example, research by Febriani and Sa'diyah (2021), Günzel-Jensen et al. (2018), and Afsar et al. (2014) indicates that leadership, including Islamic leadership, positively and significantly contributes to innovative behavior. Therefore, this study further strengthens and supports previous research on the significance of Islamic leadership in influencing innovative behavior.

Research findings confirm that digital literacy significantly influences innovative behavior. The ability to access, evaluate, and utilize digital information fosters creative ideas and adaptation to technology. Digital literacy also accelerates innovative problem-solving through information access and critical thinking. Digitally literate individuals are better able to keep up with trends

and remain competitive. In the digital era, healthcare professionals are required to optimize technologies such as electronic medical records and telemedicine to improve services. Therefore, improving digital literacy is key for healthcare professionals to innovate and provide quality services. These findings align with previous research by Pilav-Velić et al. (2021) and Putra et al. (2023) which demonstrated that digital literacy positively contributes to increasing innovative behavior. These studies demonstrated that individuals with high levels of digital literacy are better able to access, analyze, and utilize technology to create innovative solutions. Therefore, improving digital literacy in the workplace can be an effective strategy to foster an innovative culture and increase organizational competitiveness. This is no exception in the hospital environment, where healthcare professionals are required to have strong digital literacy.

Knowledge sharing, based on the results of hypothesis testing, has also been shown to be a significant factor influencing innovative behavior. Therefore, if knowledge sharing is well-developed, it has the potential to positively encourage innovative behavior. This can occur because knowledge sharing within an organization is essential for disseminating information and improving individual skills that support work processes. Strong knowledge sharing behavior can be a key asset in encouraging individual innovation. Innovation requires adequate knowledge, skills, and information, which can be obtained through knowledge sharing. Mullins (2016) states that successful companies are those capable of rapidly creating, disseminating, and applying new knowledge.

Organizations that encourage a culture of knowledge sharing will be better equipped to produce innovative products or services. Thus, knowledge sharing plays a crucial role in enhancing individual innovative behavior within the organization. Gordon (2010) also emphasized that a culture that encourages creativity, collaboration, and open knowledge sharing will strengthen an organization's innovation capabilities. Therefore, companies need to build a culture of knowledge sharing so that organizational members can exchange useful information in completing work.

Islamic leadership, in addition to influencing innovative behavior, has also been confirmed to influence knowledge sharing. This suggests that in healthcare organizations such as hospitals, the implementation of Islamic leadership is crucial because it can strengthen a culture of knowledge sharing among healthcare workers. Leaders grounded in Islamic values tend to encourage openness, trust, and collaboration within teams, which are the primary foundations for creating an effective flow of knowledge. With a strong culture of knowledge sharing, hospitals can improve service quality, accelerate medical innovation, and create a supportive work environment. This finding aligns with previous research by Park and Kim (2018), which found leadership directly influences the knowledge-sharing climate and knowledge-sharing behavior, as well as research by Kim and Park (2020) and Saeed et al. (2022), which demonstrated leadership as a predictor of knowledge-sharing behavior.

In addition to being influenced by Islamic leadership, knowledge sharing is also influenced by digital literacy. These findings demonstrate that in the digital era, strong digital literacy is a crucial foundation for creating a climate of knowledge sharing in the hospital environment.

Healthcare workers with digital literacy skills are able to access, manage, and share medical information more effectively and efficiently. This encourages interprofessional collaboration, the exchange of ideas, and the dissemination of best practices in healthcare. Thus, digital literacy not only supports digital transformation in hospitals but also strengthens a knowledge-based organizational culture. The results of this study align with a study by Sulehri et al. (2024), which found that digital literacy can influence knowledge sharing. Similarly, a study by Salimi et al. (2025) concluded that digital literacy significantly influences knowledge sharing.

The findings of this study also demonstrate that knowledge sharing mediates the influence of Islamic leadership and digital literacy on innovative behavior. This mediating role in the hospital context is crucial, as it serves as a bridge between Islamic leadership and digital literacy on the innovative behavior of healthcare workers. The findings indicate that knowledge sharing significantly strengthens the influence of Islamic leadership on innovative behavior, meaning that leaders who prioritize Islamic values can foster a collaborative and open work culture. Through this culture, healthcare workers are more encouraged to exchange relevant information and experiences to improve the quality of care. Similarly, high digital literacy enables healthcare workers to access and disseminate medical information quickly and accurately, and this process is reinforced through knowledge sharing. When knowledge sharing is effective, clinical information and innovations can be disseminated more evenly and quickly throughout the organization. Thus, knowledge sharing is key to optimizing the influence of leadership and digital literacy on innovation in hospitals.

The results of this study have important theoretical implications in strengthening and expanding the theory of Islamic leadership, digital literacy, and knowledge sharing within the context of healthcare organizations. First, the findings confirm that Islamic leadership not only reflects spiritual value-based work ethics but also positively impacts innovative behavior by fostering a collaborative work culture. Second, this study broadens the understanding of digital literacy as a key driver of innovation in the digital era, especially in work environments that heavily rely on technology such as hospitals. Third, the discovery that knowledge sharing mediates the relationship between Islamic leadership and digital literacy toward innovative behavior contributes theoretically by enriching organizational innovation models grounded in knowledge and spiritual values.

Practically, the findings provide strategic direction for hospitals, particularly Islamic-based hospitals, in enhancing the innovative behavior of healthcare workers. First, there is a need to develop leadership training that integrates Islamic values to create an open, trustworthy, and collaborative work climate. Second, hospitals must actively improve the digital competence of their healthcare personnel through training and the provision of supportive digital tools.

Third, it is important for hospital management to build strong systems and cultures of knowledge sharing, such as inter-professional discussion forums, internal information-sharing platforms, and reward systems for individuals actively sharing knowledge. These efforts will strengthen the foundation of an innovative and adaptive organization in addressing modern healthcare service challenges.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that Islamic leadership and digital literacy have a significant and positive influence both on knowledge sharing and the innovative behavior of healthcare workers. Leaders who apply Islamic values are not only seen as role models but also act as enablers of a supportive, ethical, and collaborative work environment. Such leadership encourages openness, mutual trust, and teamwork, which are essential elements for innovation to thrive. Islamic leadership also nurtures values like accountability, continuous self-improvement, and service to others—principles that align with the goals of healthcare innovation. Likewise, digital literacy empowers healthcare professionals to access, analyze, and utilize digital information efficiently in their daily tasks. This capability enhances responsiveness to patient needs, enables data-driven decision-making, and supports the use of technology for innovative healthcare solutions. The study further reveals that knowledge sharing plays a pivotal role in mediating the influence of both Islamic leadership and digital literacy on innovation. When knowledge sharing is actively practiced, it facilitates the dissemination of new ideas, skills, and clinical expertise among team members. This shared knowledge accelerates innovation by fostering collective learning and continuous improvement in healthcare services. Moreover, digitally literate individuals are more inclined and better equipped to engage in knowledge sharing, as they can easily manage and distribute information using digital tools. Leaders who promote a knowledge-sharing culture amplify this effect by encouraging collaboration, communication, and knowledge exchange. Therefore, building and sustaining a culture of knowledge sharing is essential for maximizing the impact of Islamic leadership and digital literacy in driving innovation across healthcare organizations.

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